
ASSESSMENT OF THE FACTORS INFLUENCING GIRL-CHILD EDUCATION IN BIRNUWA AND DUTSE ZONES OF JIGAWA STATE, NIGERIA

BY

HAJIYA GAJI HUSSAINI¹
SA'ADATU YAYA ABUABAKAR²

¹DEPARTMENT OF GENERAL STUDIES
²DEPARTMENT OF BANKING AND FINANCE
HUSSAINI ADAMU FEDERAL POLYTECHNIC KAZAURE,
JIGAWA STATE, NIGERIA.

Abstract

This study was conducted in line with examining the study is to access the factors influencing girl's-child education in Jigawa state Nigeria, while the specific objectives are to: Describe the socio-economic of the respondents of the respondents in the study area. Assess the factors influencing girl's-child education explained by teachers in the study area. Assess the factors influencing girl's-child education explained by students in the study area. Data were collected through structured questionnaire with a cross sectional design. Descriptive and correlational tools were used. Findings from the study revealed that amongst the several factors affecting girl child education, early marriage ideology negatively and significantly influence girl child education, Lack of basic school facilities (teaching aids, teacher's quarters, staff training seminars etc.), Illiteracy of the parents. This implies that as the people hold their sociocultural belief with high esteem as regard to early marriage, the girl-child suffers more as she is predisposed to high ignorance which to a large extent affects her interaction in the society at large. The study recommends that, the issue of early marriage should be discouraged, this can be through the passage of the child rights bill in all the states of the federation

Keywords: Girl-child, education.

TETFUND SPONSORSHIP

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The term girl-child is a female child between the ages of 16-18 years (Mukhtar, 2011). Jakaiye (2017) defines the girl as a biological female offspring from birth to 18 years of age. During this period the young girl is totally under the care of the adult who may be parent, guardian or elder siblings. She is very dependent on the others on who she is models her behaviour, repetition and imitation. Her physical mental, spiritual an emotional development start and progress to get to the peak at the young adult stage (Dauda, 2013).

Girl-child has become a major issue of concern in most developing countries of the world today, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa, where many young girls do not attend school. In Sub-Saharan Africa the number of girls out of school each year has risen from 20 million in 1990 to 24 million in 2002 (Offorma, 2009). According to the former Nigerian president Muhammadu Buhari as quoted on January 16, 2020 Nigeria has 13.2 million out of school children. The girl-child accounts for 60% of this figure. In the northern part of Nigeria which comprises of three geo-political zones, the north-east, north-central and north-west. The north-central cannot boast of appreciable number of girls enrolment at primary and secondary schools level, not to talk of tertiary level of education as compared to men in the regions. In order to accomplish the goal of education for all and gender equality based on international agreement, Nigerian government both at the federal and state levels adopted and implemented some of the declaration especially MDG's and EFA by setting up structures toward the achievement of these goals (Bakwai, Yisa and Jega, 2022). Despite all these multisectoral efforts to achieve gender equality in education, Nigeria is still experiencing wide regional and disparity in education.

Education is a key to societal development this has been recognized globally. It is equally through the use of education that, the environment has been transformed into a better place to live. Proper utilization of resources brings out the best on child's education. To achieve human capital development, it is necessary that education is obtainable and affordable, lack of education will have negative influences on the individual, family and society at large (UNICEF, 2017).

2.0 LITERITURE REVIEW

2.1.1 Girl-Child

According to Mamman (2015), girl is a biological offspring from birth to 18 year ages, this is the age that precede young women or adult. While a child according United Nations Committee on a right f a child as quoted by Garba (2000), is anyone who is below age of eighteen (18) years of age every human being regardless of sex, that is below of eighteen years is refer as a child. In analyzing the two definitions girl child can therefore be a biological female offspring from birth to eighteen years of age. This period covers the nursery or early childhood (0-5 years), primary (6-12 years) and secondary (12-18 years), so during this period the girl-child is totally under the care of the adult who may be her parent, guardians and other adult siblings that is the period for her physical, mental, cognitive, social, spiritual and emotional development starts to get to the peak adult stage.

2.1,2 Education

According to Mbuka and Schiller, (2014), education I the process of providing information to an inexperienced person to help individual develop physically, mentally, socially, emotionally, spiritually, politically and economically. Education is the process through which individuals are made fictional members of their society (Gomes, 2013). It is a process

through which the young acquires knowledge and realize his/her potentials and uses them for self-actualization. Education is implicitly a part of culture as it is a life-long learning process that enables a person, irrespective of age, understand the relationship between the environment and his/her peculiar circumstances. Consequently, the lack of education will have negative influences on the individual, family and society at large (WHO/UNICEF, 2017).

2.1.3 Girl-Child Education

Girl's education goes beyond getting girls into school. It is also about ensuring that girl learn and feel safe in school, could complete all levels of education acquiring the knowledge and skills to compete in the labour market, learn the socio-emotional and life skill necessary to navigate and adopt to changing world make decisions about their own lives and contributes to their community and the world at large. However, the challenges of girls-child education start at home. It is at this level in the community that girls are treated differently from boys, the parents, siblings, relatives, neighbors and society see to be completely different from boys. It is a general assumption that boys are more capable, more responsible, more significant to the society than girls. They are not given equal opportunities and attention especially in skills and education as boys to prove their capabilities. The prevalence of gender bias society is believed to be a hindrance in girls-child education as well as social discrimination between girls and boys, as lamented by Dewberry, (2015) that the girl-child is discriminated again in terms of education and give out to marriage early there by denying the girl-child the required competences for community development.

2.2 Theoretical frame work.

This study subscribed to feminism theory and Weberian analysis of power (Isaac, 2007), on the factors influencing girl-child education in Birniwa and Dutse zones in Jigawa state. Feminism is a collective term for system of beliefs and theories that pay special attention to women's right and women's position in culture and society. The theory tend to be used for the women's right movement and continues to campaign for complete political, social, economic equality between men and women.

The Nigerian women and girl-child in some part of the country hurry to regain virtues through education. In view of the fact that, the virtue of the individuals in the society has strong implication for the virtues of the society, to retain and strengthen the virtue of the society. Therefore, this study specifically deals with the development of the ideas behind that movement and their influence and impact of today's women.

Weberian theory or analysis of power explain that men's state of affairs depends on his market situations, on the major of power he has to influence the working of the market in his favour and the rewards of his skills & capability can commends in a competitive market. To actualize these, one has to have control over land or capital as well as goods and services, he must have social status, political resources and information resources more and physical resources and all these are attainable through education.

Therefore, this study also adopted the Weberian power analysis because they presented a more to the point analysis of the factors that enable the sustainability of a discriminatory educational pattern in contemporary Nigeria. Significantly, the theory believes in the social reality of the girl-child empowerment as being facilitated by unrestricted accessibility to social resources, especially education which will give the girl-child room to economic, social and political involvements in her immediate society.

3.0 Methodology

This research is carried out within two zones i.e Birniwa and Dutse zones were eight female secondary schools are considered in each zone. The secondary is based on updated availability of data. The study population comprises of 26 government officials, 26 parents, 649 teachers and 39, 484 female students from two zone (MOE 23/24 Enrolment figures). Simple random sampling procedures were adopted in selecting the eight schools in Birniwa zone i.e, GDSS GURI, GGASS GURI, GGASS BIRNIWA, GDSS BIRNIWA, GDSS KIKRIKASAMMA, GDSS TURABI, GDSS MARMA AND GDSS KADIRA and eight schools in Dutse zone (i.e, GGDSS Murabusawa, GGASS Baure, GGSS Kiyawa, Dutse Model International, Dutse Capital, GDSS Dr. Nuhu, GDSS Zai and GDSS dan Masara of Jigawa state. The random sampling selection of these schools prevented any bias that could be made by the researchers. Focus group discussion was also adopted for this study, however, the requisite dates were source through questionnaires where restrictions were made in such a way that only teachers and female students were allowed to fill them.

Focus group discussion was carried out where information obtained from parents and government officials in the two zones on the factors influencing girls-child education. Focus group discussion was also used where more information was obtained from nine parents and seven government officials in Dutse and six parents and seven government officials in Birniwa zone on the factors influencing girl's child education. The sample size was obtained by using Taro and Yamane's formula that is $N/1+N(e)^2$ for teachers and students at the two zones. The sample size for Dutse comprises of 264 students and 181 teachers, i.e 33 students and 23 teachers per school while in Birniwa zone, the sample size was 132 students & 67 teachers i.e 17 students and 9 teachers per school.

Descriptive statistics was used to achieve the objectives 1 and 6 by using frequency, percentage, Minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation. Five-point Laker scale was also used in achieving objectives 2 and 3. Focus group discussion was for objectives 4 and 5. Pearson correlation co-efficient was used for objectives 2 and 3.

4.0 Result and Discussion

Table 1. Factors Affecting Girl’s Child Education Explain by Teachers

S/N	STATEMENT	SD		DA		N		A		SA		WMS	SD	REMARK
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
1.	Lack of basic school facilities (teaching aids, teacher’s quarters, staff training seminars etc.)	11	2.9	10	2.6	14	3.7	24	6.7	12	3.2	3.23	1.32	Affected
2.	Inadequate teaching staff	7	1.8	23	6.1	5	1.3	22	5.8	14	3.7	3.18	1.35	Not Affected
3.	Long-distance to school	9	2.4	17	4.5	20	5.3	13	3.4	12	3.2	3.03	1.28	Not Affected
4.	Illiteracy of the parents	7	1.8	10	2.6	13	3.4	25	6.6	16	4.2	3.46	1.26	Affected
5.	Poor attention of parents on their daughter’s education	5	1.3	7	1.8	10	2.6	28	7.4	21	5.5	3.75	1.19	Affected
6.	Low level of government supervision and intervention	10	2.6	15	3.9	13	3.4	26	6.8	7	1.8	3.07	1.25	Not Affected

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 1 shows that, the following factors affecting girl-child education as explained by teachers are:

Lack of basic school facilities (teaching aids, teacher’s quarters, staff training, seminars etc.) affected girls-child education, illiteracy of parents affected girls-child education and poor financial status of parents on their daughters’ education is also affected girls-child education. This is in line with Adeduro (2017), who revealed that, there are some factors that affect girls-child education in the study area.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

		FAGET01	FAGET02	FAGET03	FAGET04	FAGET05	FAGET06
FAGET01	Pearson Correlation	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
	N	71					
FAGET02	Pearson Correlation	.539**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000					
	N	71	71				
FAGET03	Pearson Correlation	.276*	.297*	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.020	.012				
	N	71	71	71			
FAGET04	Pearson Correlation	.176	.336**	.275*	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.142	.004	.020			
	N	71	71	71	71		
FAGET05	Pearson Correlation	.245*	.332**	.099	.345**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.039	.005	.413	.003		
	N	71	71	71	71	71	
FAGET06	Pearson Correlation	.259*	.086	-.019	.033	.320**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.029	.476	.873	.782	.007	
	N	71	71	71	71	71	71

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 2 shows that the diagonal elements represent the correlation of each variable with itself, which is always 1.0. For example, the correlation of FAGET01 with itself is 1.0, and the correlation of FAGET01 with itself is also 1.0 and for all the other variables. The correlation between FAGET01 and FAGET02 is 0.539^{**}, indicating a significant correlation. The correlation between FAGET01 and FAGET03 is 0.276^{*}, suggesting a very weak positive correlation. The correlation between FAGET01 and FAGET04 is 0.176, indicating a very weak correlation. The correlation between FAGET01 and FAGET05 0.245^{*}, suggesting a very weak positive correlation. FAGET01 and FAGET06 is 0.259^{*} very weak positive correlation. Correlation does not imply causation, and these values only describe linear relationships.

Table 3. Factors Affecting Girl's Child Education Explain by Students

S/N	STATEMENT	SD		DA		N		A		SA		MW	SD	REMARK
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
1.	Domestic work (cooking, washing, sweeping etc.)	101	26.6	59	15.5	35	9.2	70	18.4	44	11.6	2.67	1.48	Not affected
2.	Long-distance to school	88	23.2	70	18.4	39	10.3	76	20.0	36	9.5	2.68	1.41	Not affected
3.	Inadequate social amenities at school (water, electricity, clinic etc.)	90	23.7	53	13.9	31	8.2	81	21.3	54	14.2	2.86	1.51	Not affected
4.	Marriage at early age	71	18.7	32	8.4	33	8.7	90	23.7	82	21.6	3.23	1.58	Affected
5.	Poor financial status of the parents	63	16.6	28	7.4	29	7.6	97	25.5	92	24.2	3.41	1.50	Affected
6.	Involvement in social activities (wedding, naming ceremony, etc.)	106	27.9	77	20.3	31	8.2	69	18.2	26	6.8	2.46	1.38	Not affected

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 3 shows that, the following factors listed below are affecting girl-child education as explain by students:

Marriage at early age affect girl-child education and poor financial status of parents also affect girl-child education. This is in line with Abubakar (2023), who revealed that these are some factors that affect girl-child education in the study area.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

		FAGES01	FAGES2	FAGES03	FAGES4	FAGES05	FAGES06
FAGES01	Pearson Correlation	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
	N	309					
FAGES2	Pearson Correlation	.329**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000					
	N	309	309				
FAGES03	Pearson Correlation	.211**	.438**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000				
	N	309	309	309			
FAGES4	Pearson Correlation	.146*	.266**	.287**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	.000	.000			
	N	309	309	309	309		
FAGES05	Pearson Correlation	.192**	.326**	.249**	.414**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000	.000		
	N	309	309	309	309	309	
FAGES06	Pearson Correlation	-.003	-.029	.183**	.186**	.159**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.955	.612	.001	.001	.005	
	N	309	309	309	309	309	309

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author's computation, 2025

Table 4 shows that the diagonal elements represent the correlation of each variable with itself, which is always 1.0. For example, the correlation of FAGES01 with itself is 1.0, and the correlation of FAGES01 with itself is also 1.0 and for all the other variables. The correlation between FAGES01 and FAGES02 is 0.329**, indicating a significant correlation. The correlation between FAGES01 and FAGES03 is 0.211, suggesting a very weak positive correlation. The correlation between FAGES01 and FAGES04 is 0.146, indicating a very weak positive correlation. The correlation between FAGES01 and FAGES05 is 0.192*, indicating a weak positive correlation. FAGES01 and FAGES06 is -0.003* a very weak negative correlation. These values only describe linear relationships.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

Several factors affecting girl child education, early marriage ideology negatively and significantly influences girl child education, Lack of basic school facilities (teaching aids, teacher's quarters, staff training seminars etc.), Illiteracy of the parents. In view of the research findings, the study recommends that; The issue of early marriage should be discouraged, this can be through the passage of the child rights bill in all the states of the federation.

6.0 References

- Ackroyd, S. & Hughes, J. (1989). *Data collection in context*. London: Longman.
- Adeduro, K.K. (2017). Female child education: a critical issue for National Development in Nigerian. *J. of Education and Leadership Development Vol.5, No.2, Pp. 1 – 8*.
- Bakwai, M., et al (2022). *Girl-child education: a critical issue for National Development*. University of Ado Ekiti
- Dauda, A. (2013). *New innovation on girl's education: the experience in Nigeria*. Commonwealth Education Partnership Publication.
- Dewberry, F. D. (2015). *The emancipation of women an African perspective*. Accra: Ghana Universities Press.
- Garba, K. (2002). *Ambassador for Africa: The torch biographies*. Bloomsbury Street, London: SCM Press Ltd
- Gomes, C.O. (2003). *Socio-cultural factors affecting the girl child and strategies towards the empowerment of the Nigerian girl-child*, University of Ibadan, Oyo-State, Nigeria.
- Isaac, H. B. (2007). *Policy Dialogue for Policy Makers. A Paper Presented at Stakeholders and E.F.A Coordinators in the UNIVEPD*. Field State. Maiduguri, Nigeria.
- Jakaye, A. (2017). *New innovation girl's education: the experience in Nigeria*. Commonwealth Education Partnership Publication.
- Mammam, M. (2015). *The role of community education in sustainable community*
- Mboka, A.O., & Schillar, S.K. (2014) Gender issues basic educational and national development in Nigeria. *Journal Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Study Vol4:4(21416990), 644-649*
- Mukhtar, A. (2011). *Promoting girl's education: the experience in Nigeria*. Commonwealth Education Partnership Publication.
- Offorma, D. (2009). *Rebranding Nigeria: an appraisal*. *NewsWatch Online*.